

IMPACT OF NON-GOVERNMENTAL ORGANIZATIONS ACTIVITIES ON WOMEN EMPOWERMENT IN OBIO/AKPOR LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF RIVERS STATE

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Abstract: The study focused on the Impact of Non-Governmental Organizations Activities on Women Empowerment in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State. The factors under investigation include the impact of these Non-governmental Organization activities such as the impact of skill acquisition training, family life education and reproductive health education on women empowerment in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State. In order to achieve this study, three (3) objectives of the study, research questions and null hypotheses were formulated to guide the conduct of the study. A total of Two Hundred and Fifty (250) copies of the questionnaire was administered and the entire (250) copies of the instrument were retrieved and considered usable. The data collected through the questionnaire were analyzed with arithmetic mean and standard deviation, while the hypotheses were tested with z-test, Total enumeration sampling technique was adopted for the study due to the manageable size of the population. A 4-point rating scale structured questionnaire was developed and administered to the respondents. Mean and standard deviation analysis were used for the data analysis in research questions while the null hypotheses were tested using z-test statistical tool at 0.05 level of significance. A careful analyses of the data and testing of the hypothesis revealed that Non-Governmental Organizations Activities impact women empowerment, Partnership for Transforming Health System (PATHS) and Centre for Integrated Health Partnership (CIHP) have positive and significant impact on women empowerment in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State. To this end, the researcher recommended amongst others that: Government should encourage the creation of more NGOs for women hence, it has positive impact on women empowerment in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State; Government and Non Governmental Organization should organize awareness and enlightenment campaigns on family life education because of its influence on women empowerment in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State; finally, Government should organize awareness, enlightenment campaigns on reproductive health education for women empowerment in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Keywords: Non-governmental Organizations (NGOs), Non-governmental Organizations (NGOs) Activities, Women empowerment, Community development.

1. INTRODUCTION

Non-governmental organizations (NGOs) are non-governmental, non-profit making and self-governing institutions, set out to ameliorate the plight of the people in dire need of life sustaining facilities in the society. They are bodies which function free from the control of governmental control. These are said to be non-profit governmental bodies which work

for the welfare of societies. They act as a mediator between society and government. According to Zahidi (2015), Non-governmental organizations with the support given by the government have been accelerating its development activities by taking up special issues like skill acquisition, women empowerment, poverty alleviation, child rights, caste stigma and discriminations, family life education, women rights, child labour, rural development, water and sanitation, environmental issues etc. According to Cohen (2016), Non-governmental organizations ought to develop social, capital, and human resources, encourage and motivate people to participate in activities and act as network liaisons between communities and systems. A number of these Non-Governmental organizations are into various aspects of community development such as: community mobilization, skill acquisition, family life education, environment, health and sanitation awareness creation, promotion of child's rights law, promotion of sexuality and reproductive health education and fight against child labour and human trafficking, etc.

The development of any nation hinges on the social and economic contributions of her citizens. Women empowerment results in economic sustainability, social sustainability, cultural sustainability, political sustainability and environmental sustainability (Kobani, 2021). Women empowerment activities are amongst the major component factors that promote community development. According to Kobani (2014) over the years, the Nigerian Government has advanced various programmes for community development as well as to assist the Nigerian woman. This is as a result of a perceived gender imbalance in our society that has led to the low socio-economic status of women as manifested in low literacy rates, poverty, low employment rates and low self-esteem (Kobani and Alozie, 2019). It should be known that the activities of Non-governmental organizations geared towards empowerment create a wider range of development status for any developing country like Nigeria and its rural citizens. The reasons for NGO to intervene in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State are diverse and different in nature due to the observation of marginalization of women to contribute in community development process.

Rivers State is one of the Southern States in Nigeria, where the activities of NGOs are heavily present. The NGOs have been providing the people, mostly women, with different empowerment programmes like skill acquisition training, family life education, sanitation awareness, fight against child labour, reproduction of health education and conflict resolution that enable them participate in community development in their various communities. It is as a result of the heavy presence of stereotype influence in the communities that have made some international and local NGOs to intervene in women empowerment. Some of the NGOs include: Partnership for Transforming Health System (PATHS), Balm in Gilead Foundations for Sustainable Development, Centre for Integrated Health Partnership (CIHP), amongst others in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area for (women) to contribute to community development in their different communities. Previous studies have also been carried out on the economic empowerment programmes and women participation in community development in Rivers State. For instance, Kobani (2014) study on the impact of an initiative of the former first lady of Rivers State, Judith Amaechi "Empowerment Support Initiative" (ESI), which sought to empower women and youths of Rivers State with essential skills for wealth creation through basic education. The study found out that the extent of influence of ESI on women's participation in community development in Rivers State is very low. Based on the findings, the researcher recommended amongst others that ESI should create offices in all LGAs in Rivers State to properly co-ordinate the programmes at the grassroots and that competently trained community development workers should be trained to manage the programmes.

Conceptualizing Women Empowerment

Empowerment according to the World Bank (2007) is the process of increasing the capacity of individuals or groups to make choices and to transform those choices into desired actions and outcomes. Central to this process are actions which both build individual and collective assets, and improve the efficiency and fairness of the organizational and institutional context which govern the use of these assets. Akugbue (2002) defines empowerment as a process of strengthening an existing situation, meaning that such a situation already exists that needs additional strengthening. It involves the provision of an enabling environment for productive and intellectual abilities to be realized. Empowerment is a social process, since it occurs in relationship with others. One important implication of this definition of empowerment is that the individual and community are fundamentally connected. Empowerment could be social, economic or political (Kobani and Alozie, 2019).

Social empowerment comes from all members of society being treated fairly and equally. Sociological empowerment often addresses members of groups that social discrimination processes have excluded from decision-making processes through for example, discrimination based on race, ethnicity, religion or gender. The marginalized refers to the overt or covert trends within society whereby those perceived as lacking desirable traits or deviating from the group norms tend to be excluded by wider society and ostracized as undesirables. Sometimes groups are marginalized by society at large with governments as often unwilling or enthusiastic participants. Socio-economic empowerment programmes are organized government and non-governmental bodies to educate and mobilize participants in order to encourage their meaningful contribution to the Community and the enhancement of their socio-economic status (Kobani and Alozie, 2019).

Marginalized people, who have no opportunities for sufficiency, lose their self-confidence because they cannot be fully self-supporting. The opportunities denied them also deprive them of the pride of accomplishment which others, who have those opportunities, can develop for themselves. This in turn can lead to psychological, social and even mental health problems.

Kobani and Alozie (2019) made an attempt to review some of the indicators of the influence of socio-economic empowerment programmes which would enhance the participation of women in Community development activities. They include, reduction in poverty level, unemployment, low self-esteem, illiteracy level, malnutrition, famine, environmental degradation, harmful cultural practices like female genital mutilation and widowhood practices, increase in life expectancy and healthy families, etc.

Statement of the Problem

The activities of NGOs activities on women empowerment in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area in Rivers State is basically for educational development, good access to healthcare facilities, agricultural initiatives and skills acquisition. All these activities are expected to improve women's capabilities in the local government area towards community development efforts. NGOs have trained and retrained women in these different activities and also provided services to enhance women empowerment and development in the area of study. To this effect, women beneficiaries are expected to utilize and partake in programmes and projects of community development in their various communities. The question now arises; has the different activities contributed by NGOs for women empowerment through the provision of health care services, skill acquisition, agriculture and educational initiatives in the local government area empowered the women to participate and contribute to community development in their local government area? To answer this question is the problem of the study. This study therefore, will examine the different NGOs activities for women empowerment in the area of the study and access their contributions to community development through the impact made on Beneficiaries.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study is to determine the Impact of Non-Governmental Organizations Activities on Women Empowerment in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Specifically, the objectives of the study are to:

1. Examine the impact of Partnership for Transforming Health System (PATHS) skill acquisition training on women empowerment in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State.
2. Determine the impact of Centre for Integrated Health Partnership (CIHP) family life education on women empowerment in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State.
3. Examine the impact of Balm in Gilead Foundations for Sustainable Development (BGSD) reproductive health education on women empowerment in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions will be developed by the researcher to guide the study.

1. What is the influence of Partnership for Transforming Health System (PATHS) skill acquisition training on women empowerment in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State?

2. What is the influence of Centre for Integrated Health Partnership (CIHP) family life education on women empowerment in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State?
3. What is the influence of Balm in Gilead Foundations for Sustainable Development (BGSD) reproductive health education on women empowerment in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The researcher developed the following hypotheses guided the study.

1. There is no significance difference in the mean rating of the female responses between Partnership for Transforming Health System (PATHS) skill acquisition training and women empowerment in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State.
2. There is no significance difference in the mean rating of the female responses between Centre for Integrated Health Partnership (CIHP) family life education and women empowerment in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State.
3. There is no significance difference in the mean rating of the female responses between Balm in Gilead Foundations for Sustainable Development (BGSD) reproductive health education and women empowerment in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State.

2. METHODOLOGY

The research design adopted for this study is the descriptive survey design. This design allows the researcher to observe, collect or draw specific data sample, which is a representative of a given population to describe certain characteristics, features and allow for generalization of the population, (Ahiakwo, 2015). The design is considered appropriate for this study being that the study is to describe the entire population through determining the impact of NGOs activities on women empowerment to enable sustainable Community development in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State.

The target population of the study comprised 250 women who benefited from the training of NGOs programmes namely, 27 heads of different women association groups, 73 heads of nurses from health centres and 300 heads of market women associations who constitute the total enumeration whom the NGOs directly trained to train other women which they represented the composition of population for the study in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State.

The sample of this study consists of the two hundred and fifty (250) Beneficiaries of NGOs trainings from different groups namely: head of different women association groups, head of nurses from health centres and market women associations who are the Beneficiaries from the NGOs activities in their communities in the area of study. Total enumeration sampling technique was adopted for the study due to the manageable size of the population.

Two Hundred and Fifty (250) copies of the questionnaire was administered. The data collected were analysed using weighted mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions. The criterion decision rule is that any mean score that was from 2.50 and above was 'agreed' while the mean score that is less than 2.50 is 'disagreed' while the null hypotheses was tested using z-test statistical tool at a significance level of 0.05 level of significance. The null hypotheses where z-calculated value is greater than the z-critical value of 1.96 was rejected while the null hypotheses were z-calculated value which is less than z-critical value of 1.96 was accepted.

3. DATA ANALYSIS

This section deals with the presentation of data, analysis and discussion of findings. The analysed data were used to provide answers to the research questions and test the formulated null hypotheses. The outputs of data analysis are presented in tables.

Research Question 1: What is the impact of Partnership for Transforming Health System (PATHS) skill acquisition training on women empowerment in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation analysis on the influence of Partnership for Transforming Health System (PATHS) skill acquisition training on women empowerment in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State.

S/ No	Questionnaire Items	Women Executive =30			Women Members =220		
		Mean \bar{x}	SD	Remarks	Mean \bar{x}	SD	Remarks
1.	Skill acquisition training has enabled women to become skilled in their areas of interest, for example tailoring, catering, hairdressing, craft and art creation.	2.89	0.85	Agreed	2.95	0.86	Agreed
2.	Through provision of skill acquisition training, women can generate income from learnt skills for the household.	2.86	0.83	Agreed	2.86	0.84	Agreed
3.	Skill acquisition training has empowered women not to be dependent on the male counter part, but rather women can generate resources themselves.	2.78	0.83	Agreed	2.91	0.85	Agreed
4.	Through the provision of skill acquisition training for women, it has reduced the poverty rate in the community.	2.83	0.84	Agreed	2.82	0.84	Agreed
5.	Through skill acquisition training for women empowerment, it has also helped in provision of employment for other individuals.	2.86	0.84	Agreed	2.86	0.84	Agreed
Grand Total		2.84	0.84		2.88	0.85	

Source: Field Survey, 2021

The analysis in Table 1 above revealed that the respondents agreed on the view that skill acquisition training has enabled women to become skilled in their areas of interest, for example: tailoring, catering, hairdressing, craft and art creation. The analysis still indicated that the respondents accepted to the point that through provision of skill acquisition training, women can generate income from learnt skills for the household. It was also observed in the study that the respondents accepted the fact that skill acquisition training has empowered women not to be dependent on their male counterparts, but rather women can generate resources themselves. The study still showed that the respondents agreed to the view that through the provision of skill acquisition training for women, poverty rate has been reduced in the community. The analysis also revealed that the respondents agreed to the view that through skill acquisition training for women there is provision of employment for not only the women but also for other individuals as well.

Research Question 2: What is the influence of Centre for Integrated Health Partnership (CIHP) family life education on women empowerment in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State?

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation analysis on the impact of Centre for Integrated Health Partnership (CIHP) family life education programme on women empowerment in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State.

S/ No	Questionnaire Items	Women Executive =30			Women Members =220		
		Mean \bar{x}	SD	Remarks	Mean \bar{x}	SD	Remarks
6.	CIHP family life education programme has created the awareness in women the need to keep the home clean and safe.	2.86	0.84	Agreed	2.91	0.85	Agreed

7	Through the provision of family life education programme by CIHP NGO, women have become empowered with education against child marriage and its damages to women.	2.83	0.84	Agreed	2.95	0.86	Agreed
8	CIHP family life education programme has empowered women with education to have control over sexual and reproductive health rights in their households by equipping them with important information of family health.	2.97	0.86	Agreed	2.98	0.86	Agreed
9.	CIHP family life education programme has enabled women to make decisions that will benefit them, to contribute to community development.	2.94	0.86	Agreed	2.99	0.86	Agreed
10	CIHP NGO family life education programme has provided scholarships for women and girls for their further/higher education.	2.86	0.84	Agreed	2.91	0.85	Agreed
Grand Total		2.90	0.85		2.97	0.86	

Source: Field Survey, 2021.

The data analysis in Table 2 above indicated that the respondents accepted the point that CIHP has created the family life education in the community. The analysis also showed that the respondents agreed on the view that through the provision of family life education by CIHP NGO has empowered women against child marriage and its damages to women. It was still noticed in the study that the respondents agreed on the fact that family life education has empowered women to have control over sexual and reproductive health rights in their households. The analysis also revealed that the respondents accepted the view that family life education has enabled women to make decisions that will benefit them, to contribute to community development. The study indicated that the respondents agreed to the fact that CIHP NGO family life education has provided scholarship programmes for women and the girl child for further/higher education.

Research Question 3: What is the influence of Balm in Gilead Foundations for Sustainable Development (BGSD) reproductive health education on women empowerment in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State?

Table 3: Mean and standard deviation analysis on the influence of Balm in Gilead Foundations for Sustainable Development (BGSD) reproductive health education on women empowerment in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State.

S/ No	Questionnaire Items	Women Executive =30			Women Members =220		
		Mean \bar{x}	SD	Remarks	Mean \bar{x}	SD	Remarks
11.	Provision of proper health care services by Balm in Gilead Foundation for Sustainable Development NGO has created the awareness of sexually transmitted disease in women.	2.83	0.84	Agreed	2.91	0.85	Agreed
12	The provision of health care services by Balm in Gilead Foundation for Sustainable Development has increased he knowledge on family health planning such as: control birth, safe pregnancy, safe sex, dangers of early pregnancy for the girl child.	2.72	0.82	Agreed	2.86	0.84	Agreed
13.	Through the provision of health care services by Balm in Gilead Foundation for Sustainable Development, women can have free access to HIV/Aids testing, cancer examinations, eye test, etc.	2.69	0.82	Agreed	2.95	0.86	Agreed

14	Balm in Gilead Foundation for Sustainable Development has availed women access to proper health care services and has created in them the awareness on how to manage their sexual and reproductive life.	2.83	0.84	Agreed	2.91	0.85	Agreed
15.	Balm in Gilead Foundation for Sustainable Development NGO has provided proper health care services and has helped women to combat sexual and domestic violence in the community.	2.67	0.82	Agreed	2.87	0.85	Agreed
Grand Total		2.73	0.83		2.90	0.85	

Source: Field Survey, 2021.

The analysis in Table 3 above showed that the respondents accepted the point that provision of proper health care services has created the awareness of sexually transmitted disease in women. The study still revealed that the respondents agreed that the provision of health care services has increased the knowledge on family health planning such as: birth control, safe pregnancy, safe sex, dangers of early pregnancy for the girl child. It was also observed from the analysis that the respondents accepted the point that through the provision of health care service by NGOs, women can have free access to HIV/Aids testing, cancer examinations, eye tests, etc. The analysis still indicated that the respondents agreed on the view that NGOs access to proper health care services has created the awareness in women on how to manage sexual and reproductive life. It also showed that the respondents accepted the fact that NGOs provide proper health care services to help women to combat sexual and domestic violence in the community.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significance difference in the mean rating of the female responses between NGOs and women empowerment in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Table 4: Z-test Analysis of no significance difference in the mean rating of the female responses between Partnership for Transforming Health System (PATHS) and women empowerment in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Status	N	Mean \bar{X}	SD	Df	z-cal	z-crit	Decision
Women Executives	30	2.84	0.84	248	0.29	1.96	Accepted
Women Members	220	2.88	0.85				

The analysis on Table 4 revealed that the z-cal of 0.29 is less than the z-crit of 1.96. Therefore, the calculated z-ratio is not statistically significant at a 0.05 level of significance since it is smaller than the given critical value of z-ratio. So, the hypothesis 1 is thus accepted and the conclusion is that there is no significance difference in the mean rating of the female responses between entrepreneurship training and women empowerment in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significance difference in the mean rating of the female responses between Centre for Integrated Health Partnership (CIHP) family life education and women empowerment in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Table 5: Z-test Analysis of no significance difference in the mean rating of the female responses between Centre for Integrated Health Partnership (CIHP) family life education and women empowerment in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State

Status	N	Mean \bar{X}	SD	Df	z-cal	z-crit	Decision
Women Executives	30	2.90	0.85	248	0.24	1.96	Accepted
Women Members	220	2.97	0.86				

The analysis on Table 5 indicated that the z-cal of 0.24 is less than the z-crit of 1.96. Therefore, the calculated z-ratio is not statistically significant at a 0.05 level of significance since it is less than the given critical value of z-ratio. Therefore, the hypothesis 2 is thus accepted and the conclusion is that there is no significance difference in the mean rating of the female responses between family life education and women empowerment for in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significance difference in the mean rating of the female responses between Balm in Gilead Foundations for Sustainable Development (BGSD) reproductive health education and women empowerment in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Table 6: Z-test Analysis of significance difference in the mean rating of the female responses between Balm in Gilead Foundations for Sustainable Development (BGSD) reproductive health and women empowerment in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Status	N	Mean \bar{X}	SD	df.	z-cal	z-crit	Decision
Women Executives	15	2.73	0.83	248	0.39	1.96	Accepted
Women Members	343	2.90	0.85				

The analysis on Table 6 showed that the z-cal of 0.39 is less than the z-crit of 1.96. Therefore, the calculated z-ratio is not statistically significant at a 0.05 level of significance since it is less than the given critical value of z-ratio. Therefore, the hypothesis 3 is thus accepted and the conclusion is that there is no significance difference in the mean rating of the female responses between reproductive health education and women empowerment in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State.

4. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The finding of the study in research question one: What is the influence of Partnership for Transforming Health System (PATHS) skill acquisition training on women empowerment in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State revealed that there is positive influence of Partnership for Transforming Health System (PATHS) skill acquisition training on women empowerment in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State. This finding is in collaboration with Steve (2012), who observed that skill acquisition has enabled women to become skilled in their areas of interest, for example tailoring, catering, hairdressing, craft and art creation. The analysis still indicated that the respondents accepted on the point that through provision of skill acquisition, women can generate income from learnt skills for the household. It was also observed in the study that the respondents accepted the fact that skill acquisition training has empowered women not to be dependent on the male counterpart, but rather women can generate resources themselves. The study still showed that the respondents agreed on the view that through the provision of skill acquisition training for women, it has reduced the poverty rate in the community. The analysis also revealed that the respondents agreed on the view that through skill acquisition training for women empowerment, it has also helped in provision of employment for other individuals.

The study in Research Questions 2: What is the influence of Centre for Integrated Health Partnership (CIHP) family life education on women empowerment in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State indicated that Centre for Integrated Health Partnership (CIHP) skill acquisition has significant influence on women empowerment in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State. This study is in the same view with Kabeer (2013), who noted that education initiative programme has created the awareness in women on their rights in the community with regards to abuse from spouses in the home hence, the need for family education. The analysis also showed that the respondents agreed on the view that through the provision of education initiative programmes by NGOs, it has empowered women against child marriages and its damages to women. It was still noticed in the study that the respondents agreed on the fact that education initiative has empowered women to have control over sexual and reproductive health rights in their households. The analysis also revealed that the respondents accepted the view that education initiatives have enabled women to make decisions that will benefit them, to contribute to community development. The study indicated that the respondents agreed on the fact that NGOs education initiatives have provided scholarship programmes for women and the girl child for further/higher education.

The findings of the study in Research Question 3: What is the influence of Balm in Gilead Foundations for Sustainable Development (BGSD) reproductive health education on women empowerment in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State showed that Balm in Gilead Foundations for Sustainable Development (BGSD) reproductive health education has positive influence on women empowerment in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State. The finding is in the same vein with Elliot (2018), who noted that provision of proper health care services has created the awareness of sexually transmitted diseases in women. The study still revealed that the respondents agreed that the provision of health care services has increased the knowledge on family health planning such as: birth control, safe pregnancy, safe sex, dangers of early pregnancy for the girl child. It was also observed from the analysis that the respondents accepted the point that through the provision of health care service by NGO, women can have free access to HIV/Aids testing, cancer examinations, eye tests, etc. The analysis still indicated that the respondents agreed on the view that NGOs access to proper health care services has created the awareness in women on how to manage sexual and reproductive life. It also showed that the respondents accepted the fact that the NGO gives proper health care services to help women to combat sexual and domestic violence in the community.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

The impact of Non-Governmental Organizations Activities on Women Empowerment in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State cannot be over emphasised. However, based on the findings of the study, the researcher concludes that Non-Governmental Organizations Activities like skill acquisition training on women empowerment, family life education and reproductive health education have positive and significant influence on women empowerment in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State. The study still deduced that Non-Governmental Organizations have trained and retrained women in various activities and also provided services to enhance women empowerment and development in the area of the study but some women are still not up and doing in the area of empowerment. Women beneficiaries are expected to utilize and partake in programmes and projects of community development.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made to ensure that the study meet its objectives.

- 1 Government should create more Partnership for Transforming Health System (PATHS) skill acquisition training programmes for women since it has positive influence on women empowerment in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State.
- 2 Government and Non-Governmental Organizations should organize more awareness and enlightenment campaigns through the Centre for Integrated Health Partnership (CIHP) for family life education amongst other education because of its influence on women empowerment in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State
- 3 Government should organize awareness, enlightenment campaign on Balm in Gilead Foundations for Sustainable Development (BGSD) reproductive health education on women empowerment in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State.

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